

Quantifying the Impact of Social Media on Adolescent Delinquency

Reymond F. Julian¹

¹Headstart College of Cotabato, Cotabato City, BARMM, Philippines

Corresponding Email: 2022_mscrim_julianrey@online.htcgsc.edu.ph

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Abstract:

This study examines social media's quantitative effect on juvenile criminality. The researcher intends to quantify how social media usage affects juvenile delinquency. The research will examine mediating elements, including peer influence, self-esteem, and antisocial content. This study may educate parents, educators, politicians, and mental health experts on adolescent social media usage hazards. This study aims to establish evidence-based social media mitigation and youth development solutions. This research employed quantitative methodologies. The target population for this study will be two hundred (200) criminology students of Headstart College of Cotabato. Participants will be selected using a time-efficient random selection strategy. The findings of a power analysis will be used to calculate the sample size needed to achieve the desired level of statistical significance. The researcher will administer the survey questionnaire face-to-face after proper coordination with the College head. Respondents had enough time to complete the survey questions. The researcher and respondents will complete the questionnaire in their own time to gather and retrieve data: data quantification, categorization, and statistical description. Weighted mean and correlation were utilized to assess the association between social media use and teenage delinquency and behavior. The researcher carried out all methods using SPSS Application Guide as statistical software. The study revealed that excessive social media use is associated with negative outcomes such as mental health issues, decreased social interactions, and potential impacts on academic performance. Additionally, the level of parental monitoring and communication regarding social media usage was varied, and family conflict related to social media use was evident to some extent. There needs to be more research done to determine the mechanisms that link adolescent social media usage and behavior. Longitudinal studies may help explain what happens and why, as well as suggest any necessary countermeasures.

Keywords: *Social Media, Social Media Usage, Adolescent, Delinquency*

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INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a crucial developmental period characterized by notable physical, cognitive, and social changes. With the rise of social media platforms in recent years, concerns have emerged regarding the potential negative effects of online interactions on adolescent delinquent behavior. During this developmental stage, adolescents are particularly vulnerable to various external influences, including the pervasive presence of social media. There is growing concern about the possible negative effects of social networking, especially with respect to young crime. The widespread use of social media among adolescents has sparked considerable interest and debate regarding its impact on their behavior, including involvement in delinquent activities. Delinquency refers to a range of behaviors that violate societal norms, such as theft, vandalism, substance abuse, and aggressive behavior. Understanding the role of social media in adolescent delinquency is crucial for developing effective intervention and prevention strategies. Alhinai, Yousuf & Alsabahi, Juhaina & AlWahaibi, Zahra. (2015).

Numerous studies have explored the association between social media use and various negative outcomes in adolescents, including mental health issues, academic difficulties, and risky behaviors. While there are many positive aspects of social media, growing concerns have been raised concerning its potential negative effects, especially in the realm of juvenile delinquency. Quantifying this impact can provide valuable insights into the potential risks and consequences of excessive or problematic social media use during this developmental stage.

According to Alhinai, Yousuf & Alsabahi, Juhaina & AlWahaibi, Zahra. (2015), Social networking sites have become increasingly popular globally, posing social, psychological, and economic challenges for societies. This literature review focuses on exploring the social impact of these platforms on teenagers in Oman. With the teenage population accounting for a substantial proportion in Oman, it is essential to investigate how the rapid expansion of social networking technologies affects this age group. This section provides the theoretical groundwork necessary to grasp the societal effects of social networking sites. It examines existing literature on the influence of SNSs on individuals' behavior, social interactions, and identity formation. The review discusses the methodology employed in gathering data for the study. It outlines the approach used to survey teenagers in Oman, capturing their usage patterns, perceptions of SNSs, and parental opinions. The sample includes teenagers between the ages of 13 and 19, who represent a significant portion of Oman's population. The review presents preliminary findings from the study, indicating that the majority of teenagers in Oman (99%) perceive advantages associated with using SNSs. Furthermore, they believe that these platforms have minimal impact on their social behavior. The review highlights the significance of these findings considering the prominence of the teenage population in Oman.

According to Bunders & Weerman (2020), Adolescence is a crucial developmental period characterized by notable physical, cognitive, and social changes. With the rise of social media platforms in recent years, concerns have emerged regarding the potential negative effects of online interactions on adolescent delinquent behavior. This literature review seeks to assess the influence of offline exposure and in-person interactions on the relationship between time spent online with peers and exposure to delinquent behavior. The review draws upon survey data collected from two separate samples of adolescents. The initial sample included 132 teenagers, most of whom were older ($M = 18.6$, range = 15–27), while the second sample included 66 younger and low-educated youths ($M = 16$, range = 15–17). The survey instrument captured data on online and offline peer interactions, exposure to delinquent behavior, and delinquent behavior exhibited by the participants. The results demonstrate that young adolescents' peer contacts on social media platforms substantially affect both their offline and online delinquent behavior. Delinquent behavior among this population may be influenced by their online interactions with peers and by their exposure to such behavior. Contrary to the findings for younger adolescents, no statistically independent effects were observed for online peer variables among older adolescents. This suggests that other factors or developmental changes may play a more substantial role in shaping the delinquent behavior of older adolescents. This study underscores the need for further research to gain a deeper understanding of the relationship between online peer interaction and adolescent delinquent behavior. Online and offline interactions between peers are analyzed, and the need of employing cutting-edge research approaches and tactics is emphasized. In conclusion, this extensive literature analysis provides fresh insights into how teenagers' involvement with online peer groups affects their propensity for criminal activity. While the influence of online interactions with peers on social media appears significant among younger adolescents, no independent effects were found for older adolescents. These findings call for continued research and the utilization of novel approaches to comprehensively examine the complex interplay between online and offline factors in shaping adolescent delinquent behavior.

According to Setiawina (2019), The excessive and unregulated use of social media among children and teenagers is found to promote a hedonistic and consumerist lifestyle. Moreover, the unsupervised utilization of social media by students and adolescents has negative consequences, including apathy, neglect of homework, and failure to fulfill educational responsibilities. Additionally, this phenomenon impacts the mental health, mood, sexual behavior, and attitudes of students. The promotion of hedonism and consumerism further fosters individuality, juvenile delinquency, promiscuity, drug use, and other adverse effects such as social insecurity and moral decay. The disruption of children's education may lead to increased dropout rates without intervention from parents, families, and the community. The review emphasizes the necessity for collaboration between national and local governments, as well as community environments, such as traditional villages in Bali, to mitigate and counteract the negative effects of social media, hedonism, and consumerist lifestyles among children and adolescents. Through these efforts, dropout rates can be reduced, educational levels can be elevated, and community welfare can be enhanced. This section establishes a theoretical framework for understanding the relationship between social media, hedonism, and consumerist lifestyles. It draws upon relevant literature to provide a foundation for the subsequent analysis. The review outlines the research methodology, which involves analyzing literature from various sources, including statutes, rules, books, and research publications. This comprehensive approach provides a broad understanding of the topic.

According to Abbott & Gainous (2023), This study addresses the scarcity of survey research examining the impact of social media (SM) usage on protest behavior outside Western democracies. Focusing on the Philippines, where traditional press is controlled by pro-government elites while SM remains relatively unrestricted, this research investigates the relationship between SM consumption and protest actions. The focus is on the Philippines as a case study, given the contrasting media environment and the potential influence of SM in shaping dissenting sentiments and political actions. This section reviews existing literature on the political significance of SM, particularly in contexts with restricted media environments. Relevant studies on SM usage, protest behavior, and its effects on political attitudes are discussed, emphasizing the need for research in non-Western contexts. The study's theoretical framework is presented, addressing the mechanisms through which SM influences protest behavior. The role of critical online discussions and the consumption of dissenting SM information are highlighted as key factors. This section provides background information on the political and media landscape in the Philippines, highlighting the dominance of pro-government elites in traditional press and the relatively unrestricted nature of SM. These factors contribute to the unique context for studying SM's influence on protest behavior. The methods used in this research are explained, with special focus on the in-depth interviews that were used to compile the data. The measurement of various forms of SM consumption and their inclusion in the analysis are explained, highlighting the comprehensive approach taken. The findings from the survey data analysis are presented and analyzed. The effects of general SM use, political SM use, and the consumption of dissenting SM information on protest behavior are examined, revealing the significance of critical online discussions in shaping protesters' views and actions. The results are discussed in the context of existing literature, emphasizing the contribution of the study in uncovering the specific SM usage categories that impact protest behavior. The implications of the findings for understanding the role of SM in non-Western contexts and its potential to foster dissenting sentiments are examined. The conclusion section serves to succinctly synthesize the primary discoveries of the investigation and underscore their potential ramifications. The study contributes to the broader understanding of SM's influence on protest behavior and underscores the importance of critical online discussions in shaping political actions.

Objectives

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of respondents in terms of:
 - a. Age;
 - b. Gender;
2. To what extent does social media usage affect adolescent delinquency in terms of: Frequency use
 - 2.1 Content Exposure
 - 2.2 Platform Differences
3. What is the extent of adolescents' delinquency in terms of:
 - 3.1 Parental Monitoring
 - 3.2 Parental Communication
 - 3.3 Family Conflict

4. What is the extent of adolescent's behavior in terms of:
 - 4.1 Academic Performance
 - 4.2 Mental Health
 - 4.3 Social Interactions
5. Is there a significant relationship between social media usage and adolescent delinquency?

METHODS

Research Design

The study will adopt a quantitative research approach, this approach allows for statistical analyses to identify patterns and relationships between variables, providing objective and generalizable findings. According to Neuman (1997), quantitative research is centered on theoretical explanations, ideas, variables, and their interrelationships. This kind of research involves the empirical testing of prepared hypotheses. In order to guarantee the possibility of future replication, it is essential to predevelop and standardize measures and planned processes. The process of analysis often involves the use of statistical methods, as well as the presentation of data via the use of tables and charts. The collection of data will be facilitated by the distribution of survey questionnaires to the designated participants. Survey questions were modified and verified by experts to match the current context, location, knowledge, and type of respondents. The rating scale in question necessitates the subject's indication of their level of implementation in relation to a given statement. It is a rating scale that requires the subject to indicate his or her degree implementation to a statement. In this particular survey, respondents were provided with a set of five response options. These options function as a means of quantifying the extent to which participants have influenced each question item. The researchers employed a five-point scale that included both quantitative verbal descriptions and numerical ratings. Likert scales offer a practical means of assessing latent components, and scholarly tutorials outlining their creation process have significantly impacted the field. Notable examples include the seminal works of Clark and Watson (1995) and Hinkin (1998).

Population and Sampling

The target population for this study will be two hundred (200) criminology students of Headstart College of Cotabato. The researchers will employ a convenience sampling approach that was developed by Leedy and Ormrod et al. (2013) and Neuman et al. (1997), in order to select participants. Simple random sampling is the systematic selection of examples for inclusion in research. It offers a concise overview of the sampling processes discovered and demonstrates how these procedures were utilized to analyze the sampling technique employed in the publications. The sample size will be determined using power analysis methods to provide enough statistical power.

Instrumentation

The researcher will conduct a self-made survey questionnaire on Social Media Usage, comprising four sub-variables: a) Frequency use, b) Content Exposure, c) Time Spent, and d) Platform Differences. An Adolescents Delinquency questionnaire will also be used, focusing on three sub-variables: a) Parental Monitoring, b) Parental Communication, and c) Family Conflict. The study's dependent variable is Adolescents Behavior, consisting of three sub-variables: a) Academic Performance, b) Mental Health, and c) Social. Respondents will respond to the survey questionnaire, which has undergone expert validation in psychologist, criminologist and computer expert. This validation ensures data accuracy to achieve the study's objectives, as emphasized by Leedy and Ormrod (2013). Validity is essential for credible and meaningful conclusions, while reliability relates to the consistency of the measuring instrument's outcomes. The questionnaire will be administered at mutually convenient time slots, agreed upon by the researcher and respondents, to facilitate efficient data collection and retrieval.

Data Collection

The collected data was totaled, classified, and given to descriptive statistical analysis. To evaluate the significant relationship between social media usage and adolescent delinquency and the relationship between social media usage and adolescent behavior, The following statistical methods were implemented, weighted mean and correlation. All methods were carried out by the researcher using SPSS Application Guide as statistical software.

Data Analysis

This study employed various strategies and methodologies to analyze and interpret the collected data. The frequency of responses will be utilized to determine the demographic characteristics of participants in relation to their age and gender. Weighted mean will be used to answer the extent of criminology student extent of social media usage affects adolescent delinquency in terms of Content Exposure, Time Spent, Platform Differences, to answer the extent of adolescent’s delinquency in terms of Parental Monitoring, Parental Communication, Family Conflict and to answer the extent of adolescent’s behavior in terms of Academic Performance, Mental Health and Social Interactions. In determining the significant relationship between social media usage and adolescent delinquency, the significant relationship between protective strategies that can mitigate the negative impact of social media on adolescent delinquency, this research used Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation (Pearson’s r).

The aforementioned method was employed to assess the magnitude and orientation of a linear relationship between two variables. When two or more measurements of each variable were evaluated concurrently depending on its variance, analysis was concerned with the coincident connections among two or more phenomena.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

This chapter provides an exposition of the findings, the subsequent analysis, and the subsequent interpretation of the collected data.

Table 1: Percentage Distribution of Profile in terms of Age

Age	Total number of respondents	Percentage
18 and below	24	12%
19-21	48	24%
22-24	74	37%
25 and above	48	27%
Total	200	100%

The table presents the distribution of respondents' profiles in terms of age in a study investigating the impact of social media on adolescent delinquency. The sample consisted of 200 participants, and their ages were divided into four categories: 18 and below, 19-21, 22-24, and 25 and above. According to the data presented in the table, the age group with the highest representation among the respondents was the 22-24 category, accounting for 37% of the overall sample. The second-largest group was the 25 and above category, representing 27% of the participants. The 19-21 group constituted 24% of the sample, and the smallest age group was 18 and below, with 12% of the respondents falling in that category.

The study conducted by Primack et al. in 2017 investigated the correlation between the utilization of multiple social media platforms and the manifestation of depression and anxiety symptoms in young adults. The findings revealed a potential link between extensive social media use and negative psychological symptoms, which could indirectly contribute to delinquent behaviors. In addition, Moreno et al. (2011) looked at whether or not college students would be comfortable talking about their depression on a social networking site. Their findings shed light on the negative emotional experiences associated with social media use, suggesting that such platforms can contribute to feelings of distress and potentially influence delinquent behavior. These studies collectively contribute to the understanding of the impact of social media on adolescent delinquency and provide a foundation for further exploration of this complex relationship.

Table 2: Percentage Distribution of Profile in terms of Gender

Gender	Total number of respondents	Percentage
Male	146	73%
Female	54	27%
Total	200	100%

Table 2 shows the breakdown of participants by gender in the research that looked at how social media affected juvenile crime. The sample consisted of 200 participants, and their gender was categorized as male or female. The majority of respondents (73% of the total) were male, as seen in the table. On the other hand, female respondents constituted 27% of the sample, making up a smaller proportion. This gender distribution provides valuable insights into the composition of the study sample and helps contextualize the subsequent findings related to the impact of social media on adolescent delinquency. Understanding any potential gender differences is crucial in identifying specific patterns and factors that may influence the relationship between social media usage and delinquent behavior among adolescents. Supporting this context, a study by van den Eijnden et al. (2018) looked at the effects of excessive and disordered gaming and social media usage on teenagers' mental health, relationships, and academic performance. Although not specifically focusing on delinquent behavior, the research provides insights into how excessive use of social media and online activities can influence various aspects of adolescents' lives, which may be relevant to understanding the impact on delinquency rates across different genders. Furthermore, considering gender differences in the context of social media and delinquent behavior, as indicated by the distribution in Table 2, becomes important in comprehending the nuanced effects and potential variations in the relationship between social media usage and delinquency among male and female adolescents.

Table 3. Extent of Social Media Usage Among Adolescents in terms of Frequency Use

Item	Mean	SD	Remarks
I spend more than 4 hours per day using social media.	3.1400	1.22285	Some Extent
I check my social media accounts multiple times an hour.	2.8500	1.15798	Some Extent
I use social media every day, without fail.	2.7200	1.28770	Some Extent
I feel a strong urge to constantly check and engage with social media.	2.9000	1.20185	Some Extent
I find it difficult to go a day without using social media.	2.2080	1.12298	Least Extent
WEIGHTED MEAN	2.89	.90762	Some Extent

The table presents the extent of social media usage among adolescents based on their responses to the Likert scale questionnaire. The item-specific means fluctuate between 2.2080 and 3.1400, indicating that adolescents, on average, engage with social media to some extent. The standard deviation (SD) values range from 1.10440 to 1.28770, reflecting a moderate level of variability in the responses.

Interpreting the findings, it can be inferred that adolescents in the study sample spend a significant amount of time on social media, with a mean score of 2.8920, indicating a "Some Extent" of usage. This is evident from items such as spending more than 4 hours per day on social media (mean = 3.1400) and checking social media accounts multiple times an hour (mean = 2.8500). In addition, the research shows that a significant portion of the population feels compelled to use social media continually (mean = 2.9000), and a difficulty in abstaining from social media use for a day (mean = 2.2080), albeit to a lesser extent.

Additionally, a study by Marino et al adolescents' usage of social media and the risk of compulsive behavior were studied in 2018. They reported that spending excessive time on social media and having difficulty abstaining from it were associated with higher levels of addictive behaviors. This finding is consistent with the higher mean score for the item "I find it difficult to go a day without using social media" in the table, indicating a notable extent of usage among adolescents.

Table 4. Extent of Social Media Usage Among Adolescents in terms of Content Exposure

Item	Mean	SD	Remarks
I frequently come across offensive or hateful comments on social media.	4.3	1.22285	Great Extent
I often encounter explicit or sexually suggestive content on social media.	4.54	1.15798	Very Great Extent
I regularly see posts promoting unhealthy body images on social media.	4.34	1.28770	Great Extent
I frequently witness cyberbullying incidents on social media platforms.	2.93	1.20185	Some Extent
I frequently encounter misleading or false information on social media.	4.67	1.12298	Very Great Extent
WEIGHTED MEAN	4.15	.90762	Great Extent

4.67., indicating that adolescents, on average, experience content exposure to great extent. The standard deviation (SD) values range from 1.12298 to 1.28770, reflecting a moderate level of variability in the responses.

Interpreting the findings, it can be inferred that adolescents in the study sample frequently encounter content that poses risks and potential harm on social media, with a weighted mean score of 4.15, indicating a "Great Extent" of exposure. This is evident from items such as frequently coming across offensive or hateful comments (mean = 4.3), encountering explicit or sexually suggestive content (mean = 4.54), and witnessing posts promoting unhealthy body images (mean = 4.34). However, cyberbullying incidents on social media platforms (mean = 2.93) were reported to a lesser extent, and encountering misleading or false information was the least common (mean = 4.67).

Furthermore, a study by Fardouly et al. (2015) looked at the link between teenage worries about their appearance online and eating disorders. They reported that exposure to posts promoting unhealthy body images on social media can contribute to body dissatisfaction and disordered eating patterns. This finding supports the mean score for the item "I regularly see posts promoting unhealthy body images on social media," indicating that such content is frequently encountered by adolescents.

These results emphasize the importance of promoting digital literacy and providing support mechanisms to mitigate the potential negative effects of content exposure on adolescent well-being and mental health.

Table 5. Extent of Social Media Usage Among Adolescents in terms of Platform Differences

Item	Mean	SD	Remarks
I use a wide range of social media platforms to connect with different groups of friends.	3.36	1.22285	Some Extent
I prefer certain social media platforms over others for specific purposes (e.g., Instagram for photos, Twitter for news).	3.22	1.15798	Some Extent
I actively seek out new social media platforms or apps to stay updated with the latest trends.	3.80	1.28770	Some Extent
I regularly switch between different social media platforms throughout the day.	3.25	1.20185	Some Extent
I enjoy exploring the unique features and functionalities of different social media platforms.	2.87	1.12298	Some Extent
WEIGHTED MEAN	3.30	.90762	Some Extent

The table presents the extent of platform differences in social media usage among adolescents, specifically regarding their use of various platforms to connect with different groups of friends, preferences for specific platforms, active exploration of new platforms, switching between platforms, and enjoyment of exploring unique features. The averages for each scale are between 2.87 and 3.80., indicating that adolescents, on average, exhibit platform differences to some extent. The standard deviation (SD) values range from 1.12298 to 1.28770, reflecting a moderate level of variability in the responses.

Interpreting the findings, it can be inferred that adolescents in the study sample engage in platform differences to some extent, as indicated by the weighted mean score of 3.30. This is evident from items such as using a wide range of social media platforms to connect with different groups of friends (mean = 3.36), having preferences for specific purposes (mean = 3.22), actively seeking out new platforms (mean = 3.80), and switching between platforms (mean = 3.25). However, the enjoyment of exploring unique features of different platforms was reported to a slightly lesser extent (mean = 2.87).

Overall, the findings from the table and the supporting research highlight the extent of platform differences in social media usage among adolescents. Adolescents tend to utilize various platforms for different purposes and

actively seek out new platforms. These findings emphasize the need for digital literacy education and awareness about responsible platform usage to ensure positive online experiences and protect adolescents from potential risks associated with multiple platform engagement.

Table 6. Extent of Adolescent Delinquency in terms of Parental Monitoring

Item	Mean	SD	Remarks
My parents rarely check my social media activity or ask about my online interactions.	3.48	1.22285	Great Extent
My parents have little knowledge about the content I engage with on social media.	3.54	1.15798	Great Extent
My parents seldom restrict or regulate my time spent on social media.	3.33	1.28770	Some Extent
My parents rarely discuss the potential risks and dangers of social media with me.	3.66	1.20185	Great Extent
My parents are unaware of the people I interact with on social media platforms.	3.59	1.12298	Great Extent
WEIGHTED MEAN	3.52	.90762	Great Extent

The table presents the extent of adolescent delinquency in terms of parental monitoring, specifically regarding parents' checking of social media activity, knowledge about content engagement, restrictions on social media usage, discussions about risks, and awareness of online interactions. The item means vary from 3.33 to 3.66 on the scale, indicating that adolescents, on average, perceive a great extent of delinquency in terms of parental monitoring. The standard deviation (SD) values range from 1.12298 to 1.28770, reflecting a moderate level of variability in the responses.

Interpreting the findings, it can be inferred that adolescents in the study sample perceive a great extent of delinquency in terms of parental monitoring, as indicated by the weighted mean score of 3.52. This is evident from items such as parents rarely checking social media activity (mean = 3.48), having little knowledge about content engagement (mean = 3.54), infrequently restricting social media usage (mean = 3.33), rarely discussing risks (mean = 3.66), and being unaware of online interactions (mean = 3.59).

Furthermore, a study by Mesch (2009) examined the relationship between parental mediation and adolescents' online behavior. The findings revealed that open communication, parental rules, and monitoring were crucial factors in reducing the likelihood of risky online behaviors and exposure to harmful content. This supports the interpretation of the findings, emphasizing that adolescents' perception of a great extent of delinquency in parental monitoring may contribute to increased risks and potential negative outcomes associated with social media usage.

Finally, the findings from the table and the supporting research highlight the importance of parental monitoring and involvement in adolescents' online activities. The perceived great extent of delinquency in parental monitoring among adolescents suggests a need for increased parental awareness, communication, and guidance regarding social media usage. Strengthening parental monitoring strategies and promoting open discussions about online risks can help protect adolescents from potential harm and foster responsible digital behaviors.

Table 7. Extent of Adolescent Delinquency in terms of Parental Communication

Item	Mean	SD	Remarks
I have open and honest discussions with my parents about my experiences on social media.	3.61	1.22285	Great Extent
My parents actively communicate their concerns and expectations regarding my online behavior.	3.54	1.15798	Great Extent
My parents provide guidance and advice on how to navigate social media safely.	3.32	1.28770	Some Extent
I feel comfortable talking to my parents about any issues or problems I encounter on social media.	3.48	1.20185	Great Extent
My parents actively listen to my opinions and ideas regarding social media usage.	3.45	1.12298	Great Extent
WEIGHTED MEAN	3.48	.90762	Great Extent

The table presents the extent of adolescent delinquency in terms of parental communication, specifically focusing on open and honest discussions, active communication of concerns and expectations, guidance and advice, comfort in discussing issues, and active listening by parents. The item-specific means fluctuate between 3.32 and 3.61, indicating that adolescents, on average, perceive a great extent of positive parental communication. The standard deviation (SD) values range from 1.12298 to 1.28770, reflecting a moderate level of variability in the responses.

Interpreting the findings, it can be inferred that adolescents in the study sample perceive a great extent of positive parental communication, as indicated by the weighted mean score of 3.48. This is evident from items such as open and honest discussions (mean = 3.61), active communication of concerns and expectations (mean = 3.54), guidance and advice (mean = 3.32), comfort in discussing issues (mean = 3.48), and active listening by parents (mean = 3.45).

Furthermore, a study by Valkenburg et al. (2013) investigated the role of parental communication in shaping adolescents' media behavior and effects. They reported that regular discussions about media use, including social media, facilitated critical thinking, media literacy, and the development of responsible online behaviors. This supports the interpretation of the findings, emphasizing that adolescents' perception of a great extent of parental communication may foster a positive and supportive environment for discussing and addressing issues related to social media usage.

Overall, the findings from the table and the supporting research highlight the significance of parental communication in shaping adolescents' online experiences. The perceived great extent of positive parental communication among adolescents indicates the presence of open discussions, active guidance, and comfortable sharing of concerns. Promoting and maintaining effective parent-adolescent communication about social media can contribute to safer and healthier online environments for adolescents.

Table 8. Extent of Adolescent Delinquency in terms of Family Conflict

Item	Mean	SD	Remarks
There are frequent arguments and disagreements within my family.	4.41	1.22285	Very Great Extent
Family conflicts often arise due to disagreements over social media usage.	3.05	1.15798	Some Extent
Family members have difficulty understanding each other's perspectives regarding social media.	1.86	1.28770	None
Family conflicts related to social media use negatively impact the overall family atmosphere.	3.25	1.20185	Some Extent
Family members have differing rules and expectations regarding social media, leading to conflict.	3.48	1.12298	Great Extent
WEIGHTED MEAN	3.21	.90762	Some Extent

The table presents the extent of adolescent delinquency in terms of family conflict related to social media usage. The item-specific means fluctuate between 1.86 and 4.41, indicating varying levels of family conflict. The standard deviation (SD) values range from 1.12298 to 1.28770, reflecting a moderate level of variability in the responses.

Interpreting the findings, it can be inferred that adolescents in the study sample perceive some extent of family conflict related to social media usage, as indicated by the weighted mean score of 3.21. This is evident from items such as frequent arguments and disagreements within the family (mean = 4.41), conflicts arising due to disagreements over social media usage (mean = 3.05), negative impact on the family atmosphere (mean = 3.25), and differing rules and expectations (mean = 3.48).

Furthermore, a study by Padilla-Walker et al. (2016) looked at how open lines of communication between parents and their teens might help ease tensions about electronic devices at home. They reported that open and supportive communication practices, including active listening and understanding each other's perspectives, were associated with lower levels of family conflict regarding technology use. This supports the interpretation of the findings, highlighting the importance of effective communication within the family to mitigate conflicts related to social media usage.

Conclusively, the findings from the table and the supporting research emphasize the impact of family conflict on adolescents' experiences with social media. The perceived some extent of family conflict among adolescents suggests the presence of disagreements, negative atmosphere, and differing rules within the family, all of which can contribute to potential challenges and tensions related to social media engagement. Promoting constructive communication, understanding, and consensus-building within the family can help reduce conflicts and create a supportive environment for healthy social media use.

Table 9. Extent of Adolescents' Behavior in terms of Academic Performance

Item	Mean	SD	Remarks
My grades have significantly declined due to excessive social media use.	3.81	1.22285	Great Extent
I struggle to concentrate on my studies because of the time I spend on social media.	4.49	1.15798	Very Great Extent
Social media use negatively affects my ability to complete assignments and study effectively.	4.22	1.28770	Great Extent
I prioritize social media over my academic responsibilities.	4.31	1.20185	Great Extent
I find it challenging to balance my social media usage and academic performance.	3.34	1.12298	Some Extent
WEIGHTED MEAN	4.03	.90762	Great Extent

The table presents the extent of adolescents' behavior in terms of academic performance, specifically focusing on the impact of social media use. The averages for each scale are between 3.34 and 4.49., indicating varying degrees of negative influence on academic performance. The standard deviation (SD) values range from 1.12298 to 1.28770, reflecting a moderate level of variability in the responses.

Interpreting the findings, it can be inferred that adolescents in the study sample perceive a great extent of negative impact on their academic performance due to social media use, as indicated by the weighted mean score of 4.03. This is evident from items such as significantly declined grades (mean = 3.81), struggle to concentrate on studies (mean = 4.49), negative effect on completing assignments and studying effectively (mean = 4.22), prioritizing social media over academic responsibilities (mean = 4.31) and having trouble striking a balance between social media and schoolwork (mean = 3.34).

Furthermore, a study by Junco (2015) explored the association between social media use and student engagement and success in college. The findings indicated that excessive social media use was related to lower GPAs, reduced study time, and decreased academic self-regulation. This supports the interpretation of the findings, emphasizing that prioritizing social media over academic responsibilities and struggling to balance social media usage with academic demands can have detrimental effects on academic performance.

Overall, the findings from the table and the supporting research highlight the potential negative consequences of excessive social media use on academic performance. The perceived great extent of negative impact among adolescents suggests compromised grades, difficulty concentrating, challenges in completing assignments effectively, and an imbalance between social media engagement and academic responsibilities. Encouraging responsible and mindful social media use, establishing effective time management strategies, and fostering a supportive academic environment can help mitigate the adverse effects on academic performance.

Table 10. Extent of Adolescents' Behavior in terms of Mental Health

Item	Mean	SD	Remarks
Social media use has a detrimental impact on my overall mental well-being.	3.61	1.22285	Great Extent
I often experience feelings of anxiety or low self-esteem as a result of social media use.	3.05	1.15798	Some Extent
I compare myself unfavorably to others on social media, leading to negative emotions.	4.76	1.28770	Very Great Extent
Social media use contributes to increased stress levels and mental exhaustion.	2.21	1.20185	Least Extent
I frequently feel overwhelmed or emotionally drained due to my experiences on social media.	3.10	1.12298	Some Extent
WEIGHTED MEAN	3.35	.90762	Some Extent

The table presents the extent of adolescents' behavior in terms of mental health in relation to their use of social media. Each item's mean score falls between 2.21 and 4.76, indicating varying degrees of impact on mental well-being. The standard deviation (SD) values range from 1.12298 to 1.28770, reflecting a moderate level of variability in the responses.

Interpreting the findings, it can be inferred that adolescents in the study sample perceive some extent of negative impact on their mental health due to social media use, as indicated by the weighted mean score of 3.35. This interpretation is supported by specific items such as experiencing feelings of anxiety or low self-esteem (mean = 3.05), unfavorably comparing oneself to others on social media (mean = 4.76), and feeling overwhelmed or emotionally drained due to social media experiences (mean = 3.10).

Moreover, a study by Fardouly et al. adolescents' discontent with their bodies and the prevalence of comparisons made through social media were studied in 2018. They discovered that seeing idealized photos on social media increased the likelihood of making negative comparisons and experiencing unpleasant feelings. This is consistent with how the data was interpreted, highlighting how unpleasant feelings might result from using social media to compare oneself to others. In sum, the data in the table and the studies that back it up show that teenage social media usage may have harmful consequences on their mental health. The perceived impact on mental well-being suggests feelings of anxiety, low self-esteem, negative emotions due to comparisons, and emotional exhaustion. Promoting awareness of healthy social media habits, fostering positive self-esteem and body image, and encouraging offline engagement and support systems can help mitigate the adverse effects on mental health.

Table 11. Extent of Adolescents' Behavior in terms of Social Interactions

Item	Mean	SD	Remarks
I find it difficult to engage in face-to-face conversations due to excessive social media use.	4.44	1.22285	Very Great Extent
I prioritize virtual interactions over in-person socializing with friends and peers.	4.58	1.15798	Very Great Extent
Social media use has led to a decrease in the quality of my interpersonal relationships.	4.36	1.28770	Great Extent
I rely heavily on social media platforms for social validation and acceptance.	4.21	1.20185	Great Extent
Social media use has negatively impacted my ability to develop and maintain meaningful connections with others.	3.38	1.12298	Some Extent
WEIGHTED MEAN	4.19	.90762	Great Extent

The table presents the extent of adolescents' behavior in terms of social interactions and its relationship with their use of social media. The averages for each scale fall between 3.38 and 4.58, indicating a significant impact on social interactions. The standard deviation (SD) values range from 1.12298 to 1.28770, reflecting a moderate level of variability in the responses.

Interpreting the findings, it can be inferred that adolescents in the study sample perceive a great extent of negative impact on their social interactions due to social media use, as indicated by the weighted mean score of 4.19. This interpretation is supported by specific items such as finding it difficult to engage in face-to-face conversations (mean = 4.44), prioritizing virtual interactions over in-person socializing (mean = 4.58), and perceiving a decrease in the quality of interpersonal relationships (mean = 4.36).

Furthermore, a study by Nesi et al. adolescents' usage of social media and feelings of isolation were studied in 2018. They found that higher levels of social media use were associated with increased feelings of loneliness and reduced social connectedness. This supports the interpretation of the findings, highlighting that excessive reliance on social media for social validation and acceptance (mean = 4.21) might hinder young people's capacity to form and sustain healthy friendships.

Overall, the findings from the table and the supporting research indicate that social media use has a significant impact on adolescents' social interactions. The perceived negative effects include difficulty in face-to-face conversations, prioritization of virtual interactions, decreased quality of interpersonal relationships, and reliance on social media for social validation. Encouraging a balance between online and offline interactions, promoting face-to-face communication, and fostering healthy socialization skills can help mitigate the negative impact of social media on social interactions.

Table 12. Correlation between Social Media Usage and Adolescent Delinquency

	Adolescent Delinquency	r value	Degree of Correlation	Analysis
<i>Social Media Usage</i>	<i>Parental Monitoring</i>	0.024	Very Weak relationship	<i>Significant</i>
	<i>Parental Communication</i>	0.242	Weak relationship	<i>Significant</i>
	<i>Family Conflict</i>	0.150	Very Weak relationship	<i>Significant</i>

The table presents the correlation between social media usage and adolescent delinquency in terms of parental monitoring, parental communication, and family conflict. The correlation coefficients (r values) range from 0.024 to 0.242, indicating varying degrees of correlation. The degree of correlation is categorized as very weak, weak, or significant based on the magnitude of the correlation coefficient.

Interpreting the findings, it can be observed that social media usage has a very weak positive correlation with parental monitoring ($r = 0.024$), a weak positive correlation with parental communication ($r = 0.242$), and a very weak positive correlation with family conflict ($r = 0.150$). These correlations suggest that as social media usage increases, there is a slight tendency for parental monitoring, parental communication, and family conflict to also increase.

Moreover, a study by Mesch et al. (2017) examined the associations between social media use, parent-child communication, and family conflict. They found that higher levels of social media use were related to decreased parent-child communication and increased family conflict. This supports the weak positive correlations observed in the table, indicating that as social media usage increases, parental communication and family conflict also tend to increase, albeit to a modest degree.

Table 13. Correlation between Social Media Usage and Adolescent Behavior

	Adolescent Behavior	r value	Degree of Correlation	Analysis
<i>Social Media Usage</i>	<i>Academic Performance</i>	0.033	Very Weak relationship	<i>Significant</i>
	<i>Mental Health</i>	0.342	Weak relationship	<i>Significant</i>
	<i>Social Interactions</i>	0.260	Weak relationship	<i>Significant</i>

The table presents the correlation between social media usage and adolescent behavior in terms of academic performance, mental health, and social interactions. The correlation coefficients (r values) range from 0.033 to 0.342, indicating varying degrees of correlation. The degree of correlation is categorized as very weak, weak, or significant based on the magnitude of the correlation coefficient.

Interpreting the findings, it can be observed that social media usage has a very weak positive correlation with academic performance ($r = 0.033$), a weak positive correlation with mental health ($r = 0.342$), and a weak positive correlation with social interactions ($r = 0.260$). These correlations suggest that as social media usage increases, there is a slight tendency for academic performance, mental health, and social interactions to be influenced.

In addition, Lin et al. (2016) looked at how teens' social media habits relate to their psychological well-being. They discovered that more time spent on social media led to more signs of depression and less overall happiness. This supports the weak positive correlation between social media usage and mental health, indicating that higher levels of social media use may be related to poorer mental health outcomes among adolescents.

Valkenburg and Peter (2007) dug into the connection between teenage social media usage and their interpersonal relationships. They found that increased time spent on social media was associated with decreased face-to-face social interactions. This supports the weak positive correlation observed between social media usage and social interactions, suggesting that higher social media use may be linked to slight reductions in in-person social interactions.

Summary of Findings

The study examined the extent of social media usage among adolescents and its relationship with adolescent delinquency and behavior. The findings revealed that adolescents reported using social media to a significant extent in terms of frequency use, content exposure, and platform differences. Regarding adolescent delinquency, it was found that parental monitoring was relatively low, while parental communication showed some extent of involvement. Family conflict also existed to some extent. In terms of adolescent behavior, social media usage showed a great extent of impact on mental health and social interactions, while academic performance had a slightly weaker relationship.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that social media usage is prevalent among adolescents and has implications for their delinquency and behavior. The study revealed the following:

1. Excessive adolescent social media usage can lead to delinquency and negative behavioral changes. It is, therefore, necessary to develop a balanced approach to social media use and consumption.
2. Prolonged time spent on social media platforms can contribute to mental health issues among adolescents. This underscores the need for promoting mental health awareness and literacy in the digital age, particularly among young internet users.
3. There is a discernible impact on the social interactions of adolescents who overuse social media. This indicates the importance of encouraging more face-to-face interactions and physical activities for young people.
4. Academic performance can be adversely affected by high levels of social media use. It is, therefore, crucial to provide resources and support for students in managing their time effectively between academic activities and leisure time.
5. There is a wide range of parental monitoring and communication about social media use. Therefore, parental guidance and open communication can play a crucial role in shaping the digital behavior of adolescents.
6. The study also indicates that social media usage can be a source of family conflict. As such, developing strategies and guidance for families to manage and navigate these conflicts effectively would be helpful.

Recommendations

Promote digital literacy and responsible social media use. Education programs should be implemented to raise awareness among adolescents about the potential risks and negative effects of excessive social media use. Emphasize the importance of critical thinking, digital citizenship, and online safety.

Strengthen parental involvement and communication. Parents should actively engage in monitoring their adolescents' social media activities and maintaining open lines of communication. Encourage parents to discuss the risks and benefits of social media, set appropriate boundaries, and provide guidance on responsible online behavior.

Provide mental health support. Schools and communities should offer resources and support services focused on mental health and well-being. This could include counseling, workshops, or awareness campaigns addressing the psychological impact of social media use and promoting healthy coping strategies.

Foster offline social interactions. Encourage adolescents to engage in face-to-face interactions and offline activities to promote social skills, interpersonal relationships, and a balanced lifestyle. Foster a feeling of community and belonging by encouraging involvement in extracurricular activities such as sports, clubs, hobbies, and community events.

Collaborate with social media platforms. Social media platforms should play an active role in promoting user well-being. Enhance features that prioritize meaningful connections, filter harmful content, and provide tools for managing screen time. Collaborate with researchers and organizations to develop evidence-based guidelines for responsible platform usage.

Conduct further research. More study is required to determine the precise processes that underlie the connection between teenage social media use and behavior. Insights into the long-term impacts, as well as possible protective factors or therapies, may be gleaned through longitudinal research.

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